

Efficient Pattern-Based Analysis of Network Flows in IoT Systems

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Abstract—The exponential growth of IoT deployments introduces new challenges in real-time network security and behavioral monitoring. Existing Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and activity analysis tools often face significant limitations when scaling to high-volume, high-speed IoT data streams. This paper proposes a novel framework that leverages advanced data series indexing methods, building upon our previous work and ULISSE’s variable-length subsequence indexing, to enable scalable, real-time pattern matching for IoT network flow analysis. We detail algorithmic steps for in-memory indexing, multidimensional flow analysis, and adaptive similarity search to enhance detection accuracy and efficiency. An experimental roadmap for validation on realistic IoT datasets is presented.

Index Terms—IoT Security, Network Flow Analysis, Intrusion Detection, Activity Recognition, Data Series Indexing, Real-Time Analytics

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of IoT systems in smart cities, industrial automation, and healthcare has resulted in vast volumes of network traffic. These devices, often resource-constrained, face mounting risks from evolving cyber-threats. Continuous monitoring and rapid intrusion/anomaly detection are critical, but traditional intrusion detection frameworks often fail to keep pace with IoT traffic velocity and heterogeneity.

Related Work: Signature-based IDS such as Snort [1] and Suricata [2] are foundational, but are known to struggle in high-throughput IoT contexts due to exhaustive pattern scans. IoT-tailored frameworks such as SVELTE [3] and CBSigIDS [4] optimize signature distribution and detection, but often lack flexibility for novel attacks.

Dimensionality reduction methods such as SAX [5] have been employed for IoT pattern compression [6], offering compactness but limited adaptability to patterns of variable length. SAX-based methods rely on fixed-size segmentation, which hinders dynamic flow analysis in heterogeneous IoT environments.

Recent indexing approaches, such as ULISSE [7], introduced a scalable framework for variable-length subsequence search. ULISSE’s innovation in summarizing overlapping subsequences into compact envelopes enables fast, accurate

matching, a key inspiration for our work. Previous studies such as IoTMosaic [8] and [9] showcase activity recognition from IoT flows, while fall-curve-like methods [10] focus on fault detection using signature-based approaches. Other works explore efficient traffic analysis for anomaly detection. For example, [11] proposes a locality-sensitive hash method to detect anomalous IoT flows, demonstrating lightweight scalability in resource-constrained settings.

Although progress has been made, the integration of high-performance, real-time, and adaptive indexing for IoT traffic pattern detection remains limited, underscoring the relevance of our work.

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We introduce a modular system comprising advanced in-memory indexing and variable-length subsequence search based on the ULISSE principles [7].

A. Flow Representation and Preprocessing

Raw IoT network flows are transformed into multidimensional time series by extracting packet sizes, interarrival times, byte counts, and protocol IDs. These features form high-granularity sequences reflecting behavioral nuances of IoT devices.

B. Enhanced ULISSE Indexing

We build on ULISSE’s single-index structure to support fast similarity search for subsequences of varying lengths. Our key enhancements include:

- **Multi-feature fusion:** extending ULISSE to index multidimensional flow features using a composite distance metric (e.g., weighted Euclidean norm) for richer pattern detection.
- **Real-time incremental updates:** implementing online index updates as new traffic arrives, avoiding costly re-indexing while ensuring responsiveness.
- **Contextual partitioning:** dividing the index space based on device categories (e.g., sensors, cameras) to improve matching relevance.
- **Template-based search:** incorporating known attack and anomaly templates for rapid similarity queries using k-NN over the index.

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C. Workflow Pipeline

The proposed system follows a streamlined workflow designed for efficiency and scalability in real-time IoT traffic analysis. Network flow data is continuously ingested from devices, ensuring uninterrupted IoT monitoring with minimal overhead. This raw data undergoes a feature engineering phase, where it is transformed into normalized, multidimensional time series representations suitable for both short-term and long-term pattern analysis. The indexing stage employs a dual strategy, combining high-speed in-memory indexing with an adaptive ULISSE-based variable-length subsequence indexing module, enabling both rapid access and scalable pattern matching across heterogeneous data streams. During the querying phase, incoming flow patterns are matched against stored signatures, whether fixed-length or dynamic, enabling low-latency detection of anomalies, threats, or distinctive device activities, supporting intrusion detection and behavioral monitoring. Upon identifying significant pattern matches, the system generates alerts based on configurable thresholds and integrates with security systems, incident response pipelines, and analytics modules.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PLAN

Evaluation will use TON_IoT [12] and CICIDS [13], covering diverse normal and attack scenarios. IoT device classification uses the UNSW HomeNet dataset [14]. The experimental evaluation will focus on the following key metrics:

- Detection accuracy: assessed via standard metrics (true positive rate, false positive rate, precision, recall) to quantify correct pattern identification and minimize false alarms.
- Query latency: measured as the elapsed time from the arrival of a pattern query (or the appearance of a malicious pattern in the traffic flow) to the issuance of an alert. This metric reflects the system's responsiveness, which is critical for real-time applications.
- Indexing throughput: calculated as the number of flows or subsequences the system processes and indexes per second. This measures the system's ability to keep pace with continuous high-volume IoT data streams.
- Scalability: evaluated by systematically increasing the dataset size and measuring the impact on both query latency and indexing performance. We aim to demonstrate sub-linear growth in query times as the indexed dataset scales.
- Resource efficiency: assessed by monitoring memory consumption and CPU utilization during both indexing and querying phases, allowing comparison to baseline approaches.

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed framework, we aim to benchmark its performance against several established baselines. First, we will include Suricata IDS, a widely adopted signature-based IDS that serves as a reference point for conventional pattern matching performance. This baseline allows us to compare our approach to industry-standard methods that rely on predefined attack signatures. Additionally,

we will evaluate an SAX-based pattern matching approach, which applies symbolic aggregation techniques to IoT traffic for dimensionality reduction. This comparison provides insight into the trade-offs between data compactness and detection precision when using symbolic presentations. Finally, we will incorporate a sliding window Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) baseline approach, which performs subsequence similarity searches without indexing. This baseline acts as a reference for accuracy and computational overhead, illustrating the performance gains of our indexing framework over full-sequence scans.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work introduces a scalable framework that integrates ULISSE-based variable-length subsequence indexing with multi-feature flow analysis to support comprehensive IoT network traffic monitoring. The design enables real-time detection of complex behavioral patterns in heterogeneous IoT environments, addressing security and activity recognition. Future directions include incorporating adaptive learning to enhance responsiveness to evolving threats and exploring deployment strategies optimized for resource-constrained edge environments.

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